

The Constitution of Mollugogenol A—A New Sapogenol from *Mollugo hirta*

(Miss) P. Chakrabarti

The isolation of two new sapogenins, mollugogenol A¹ and mollugogenol B² from *Mollugo hirta* was reported earlier. In this paper the structure of mollugogenol A is discussed.

Mollugogenol A (IIa), C₃₀H₅₂O₄ (M⁺476), m.p. 250-52° (∞)_D^{26°} + 58.5° (Pyridine) did not respond to tetranitromethane test for unsaturation. On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine, mollugogenol A furnished two triacetates (IIIa), C₃₆H₅₆O₆, m.p. 235-38° and (IIb)*, C₃₆H₅₈O₇, m.p. 230-32°. The compound IIIa unlike IIb gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. The presence of the isopropenyl group in IIIa was shown by its i.r. [$\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1640 and 900 cm⁻¹ (=CH₂)] and n.m.r. [CHCl₃, 60 Mc, a broad singlet at 4.62δ (2H, -C=CH₂) and a sharp singlet at 1.69δ (3H, =C-CH₃)] spectra. I. R. spectrum of (IIb) showed band at 3500 cm⁻¹ for a free hydroxyl group and its n.m.r. spectrum (CHCl₃, 60Mc) showed two broad signals at 1.32 and 1.41δ for the two methyl groups attached to a carbon bearing a tertiary hydroxyl group (CH₃-C(OH)-CH₃). The presence of a terminal hydroxy isopropyl group in IIb and mollugogenol A itself was evident from the peak at m/e 59 in their mass spectra. This observation, together with the fact that mollugogenol B (I), the second sapogenin isolated from *M. hirta*, was found to be a hopane derivative led to the assumption that mollugogenol A is a hopane or isohopane derivative. Mollugogenol A was finally degraded to zeorininone³ (IVa) as follows.

Oxidation of mollugogenol A with CrO₃-acetic acid furnished the monohydroxy triketone (IIc), C₃₀H₄₆O₄, m.p. 252-53° (dec.) [$\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH)] which responded to Zimmermann test for 3keto group thus locating a secondary hydroxyl group at C-3 position in mollugogenol A. This ketone on Wolf-Kishner reduction, followed by treatment with ethanolic hydrogen chloride (5%, 3hr), furnished the ketone (IVa), C₃₀H₄₈O, m.p. 178-180° [ν_{\max} 1710 cm⁻¹ (>C=O)], which was identified as zeorininone (IVa) [obtained from zeorine]³ by mixed m.p., t.l.c. and i.r. spectra. This correlation not only showed the nature of the carbon skeleton of mollugogenol A but also fixed one of the hydroxyl groups at C-6 position.

The triacetate (IIIb) on saponification (2% alc. KOH, room temp.) furnished the triol (IIIa), C₃₀H₅₀O₃ (M⁺458), m.p. 243-46°. On oxidation with CrO₃-pyridine complex, this

* Previously this product was described as a tetra-acetate.

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triol yielded the triketone (IIIc), $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_3$, m.p. 255-57°, which was readily isomerized to the α,β -unsaturated ketone (IVb), m.p. 244-48° (dec). [λ_{max} 255 m μ , ν_{max} 1668 cm^{-1}] by refluxing with ethanolic hydrogen chloride (3%, 3hr). IVb on lithium aluminium hydride reduction, followed by acid treatment, furnished the compound V (λ_{max} 243, 251 and 261 m μ), thus clearly locating the fourth hydroxyl group at C-16 position.

Recently the configuration of the isopropyl side chain in hopane derivatives has been shown to be β from x-ray analysis⁴ and other degradative experiments⁵ and on this basis the isopropyl side chain in isohopane derivatives was considered to be α . Hydrogenolysis of the hydroxyisopropyl side chain in mollugogenol A was found to be very slow and furnished mainly unreacted product together with a small amount of the saturated compound VI, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ (M^+ 460), m.p. 248-52°. In this respect mollugogenol A behaved more like isohopane⁶ rather than hopane derivatives. The three hydroxyl groups in mollugogenol A appeared to be equatorial as these could be acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine at 0°. On the basis of the observations made so far mollugogenol A may be represented as 3 β , 6 α , 16 β , 22-tetrahydroxy isohopane (IIa).

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BOSE INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA-9.

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